

Report on the Multiplier Event: Speaking BESPOC with Research Libraries (LibOCS Multiplier Event)

Link to this file: [LibOCS ME6 Evaluation Report](#)

Introduction

On April 11, 2024, the LibOCS project organised an online Multiplier Event titled "Speaking BESPOC with Research Libraries." This event aimed to promote the BESPOC (Broad Engagement in Science, Point of Contact) model and facilitate discussions on institutional support for Citizen Science (CS). This report combines the results of the assessment forms collected from external participants and the internal evaluation conducted by the LibOCS team.

Event Details

Date: April 11, 2024

Event Title: Speaking BESPOC with Research Libraries (LibOCS Multiplier Event)

Format: Online

This [LibOCS folder \(shared on our GDrive\)](#) contains:

- all presentation slides
- the registration
- screenshots with actual participation
- the raw evaluation data

Agenda and Speakers

- **14:30-14:40** LibOCS Project: A Short Introduction
Speaker: Liisi Lembinen (Tartu University)
- **14:40-15:00** The BESPOC Model At a Glance
Speaker: Tiberius Ignat (Immer Besser, a LibOCS Partner)
- **15:00-15:10** BESPOC Implementation at University of Latvia
Speaker: Gita Rozenberga
- **15:10-15:20** BESPOC Implementation at Kaunas University of Technology
Speaker: Aiste Pranckutė
- **15:20-15:30** BESPOC Implementation at Tartu University
Speaker: Lilian Neerut
- **15:30-16:00** Questions, Answers, Dialogue with Participants

Participation Data

- **Registrants:** 196
- **Actual Participants:** 54

External Evaluation

Participant Feedback

Relevance of the Event

Participants were asked to rate the relevance of the event on a scale from 1 to 10. The responses were:

- 6: 1
- 7: 1
- 8: 3
- 9: 5
- 10: 4

Importance of Institutional Support for CS

Participants were asked to rate the importance of having access to an institutional support service for CS. The responses were:

- 8: 3
- 9: 3
- 10: 8

Main Takeaways

Participants shared their main takeaways from the event:

1. Libraries can support CS.
2. I can go to the library if I need help for CS.
3. All stakeholders must be involved in supporting citizen science at institutional level.
4. How to start organizing the dialogue with top management, what to suggest for them.
5. BESPOC prototype was quite useful too.
6. More awareness.
7. Researchers need more information about this topic, more dissemination is needed.
8. Identifying what encourages or hinders civic engagement in open science, and understanding how academic libraries can facilitate citizen science activities in their regions.
9. The general population, whatever their background or belief, motivate them to get involved in the research process, using the scientific method, showing them that science is within reach of anyone who wants it.
10. Toolbox.

11. Do collaboration, partnership, and networking.

Suggested Topics for Future Webinars

Participants suggested the following topics for future webinars:

1. Libraries and Citizen Science.
2. Libraries and Open Science.
3. Systems.
4. How to conduct citizen science activities step by step.
5. Maybe to get deeper in implementing particular BESPOC modules.
6. I would like to know more about Citizen Science templates.
7. I have no preferences.
8. Citizen Science and Open Science Integration.
9. Case Studies and Success Stories.
10. Ethical and Practical Considerations.
11. Demonstrates, through simple examples, that questioning a reality or a simple observation is the beginning of an investigative process.
12. Dissemination of information about the possibilities offered by libraries.
13. Data Management & how to sustain.
14. How citizens can participate in research/gathering data of biodiversity.

Demographic Data

- **Gender:** 71.4% female, 28.6% male
- **Profession:**
 - Researcher: 14.3%
 - Research Manager or Administrator: 7.1%
 - Professor / Teacher / Lecturer: 14.3%
 - Research Librarian: 28.6%
 - Consultant: 7.1%
 - PhD Student: 14.3%
 - Other: 14.3%

Internal Evaluation

Participant Feedback

Relevance of the Event

LibOCS participants rated the relevance of the event on a scale from 1 to 10:

- 8: 2
- 10: 3

Importance of Institutional Support for CS

LibOCS participants rated the importance of having access to an institutional support service for CS:

- 5: 2
- 9: 1
- 10: 2

Main Takeaways

LibOCS participants shared their main takeaways:

1. It is really difficult without institutional support.
2. It requires preparation and cooperation between the various stakeholder groups and the institution's departments.
3. Universities should set up a support service for CS.
4. Even the small steps towards cooperation between libraries and researchers is helpful.
5. The exchange of information, knowledge, and experience between the parties involved is important. An intermediary can help here.
6. Libraries can also act as intermediaries.

Suggested Topics for Future Webinars

LibOCS participants suggested the following topics for future webinars:

1. How to increase the involvement of researchers in citizen science projects, how to inspire them to initiate CS projects.
2. BESPOC elements.
3. Functional services at universities volunteers and connections between researchers and volunteers.
4. Practical examples.

Demographic Data

- **Profession:**
 - Researcher: 20%
 - Professor / Teacher / Lecturer: 20%
 - Research Librarian: 60%

Conclusion

The Multiplier Event "Speaking BESPOC with Research Libraries" successfully engaged a diverse group of participants and highlighted the importance of institutional support for Citizen Science. Both external and internal evaluations indicate a strong interest in further exploring the role of libraries in supporting CS and the BESPOC model. The feedback gathered will guide the LibOCS partners in further dissemination, the organisation of future events, and engagement strategies and will generally enhance

the LibOCS project's efforts in promoting and implementing effective support structures for Citizen Science.